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Parent-Child Relationship and Emotional Intelligence: A Literature Review

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Abstract:

The research for the review of literature is one of the first and foremost important steps in the research process. The search for related literature is a time-consuming but fruitful phase of any research program. The researcher attempted to present findings from the related literature on parent-child relationships and the emotional intelligence of adolescents in this article. Reviewing related material is the major goal of this paper. To guide future study, this paper also summarises the results of studies on parent-child relationships and the emotional intelligence of adolescents.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, Parent-child Relationship, Adolescents, Cultural Pattern, Family Environment*

Introduction

The quality of any kind of social relationship is not inherited; it is shaped by our social environment depending on the cultural pattern, ethnicity, norms, and other several factors of the particular society. The relationship between parent and child is a special one that is greatly influenced by a variety of elements, including social, psychological, and cultural patterns. An essential component of a child's development and mental welfare is a good and supportive interaction between parents and children. Regardless of socio-geographic diversity or cultural differences, it is still important to carefully consider how parent-child relationships affect a child's entire identity while they are at secondary school in a certain place.

Adolescence is the period of life between childhood and adulthood. The biological and maturational changes take place at this time. Indeed, it is a time of both emotional and physical growth and transformation. Adolescence is typically a period when many earlier developments are amended or developed into more sophisticated forms. Unquestionably, the bodily changes that make a child become an adult are the driving forces behind an adolescent's growth. Adolescents experience social changes as a result of these changes, which have an impact on both their cognitive and emotional development. They make an effort to detach themselves from the family and extend their emotional dependence outside of it. They strive to become less reliant on their family so that they may navigate the world on their own.

During this time, they start to feel more independent, which inspires them to take their own decisions. During this period, peer influence is increasingly prevalent as adolescents try to establish themselves as independent, well-known figures among their peers after moving out of reach of their parents. At this point, there is a noticeable increase in closeness among the peer

groups. Sometimes, the emotional bond with friends is stronger than the one with parents. As the child moves into adolescence they learn to express themselves in different contexts. They express their opinion regarding different things in different situations effectively. They tend to rely on those people who are also going through the same phase.

However, the emotional development of the child during adolescence depends on the care and the quality environment provided during the early stage of development. As the child is emotionally weak and sensitive during this time, parents and society have a crucial role to play because they can help prevent the youngster from becoming influenced or engaging in unlawful actions. During this phase, the youngster goes through a full process of brainstorming. They may become in turmoil as a result of incorrect instruction given to them, which will disrupt their entire process of mental development. Adolescents have a lot of energy and eagerness to do something bigger and better, and occasionally their strong emotions might even direct what they do. If adolescents are not properly guided during adolescence, they may engage in criminal activity and experience negative consequences on their emotional health and interpersonal connections.

As youth culture becomes more commercialized and exploitive the context in which most adolescents must reach full independence becomes an increasingly negative factor in their emotional growth. When a youngster enters puberty, they learn the proper way to express their emotions in various situations. If the child's upbringing and past experiences have been unhealthy, it becomes difficult for adolescents to manage and control their emotions. The long-term development of a child will be impacted if they are raised in a home where arguments between the parents occur frequently or daily. Instead, it will persuade the youngster to repeat those actions in the future. The child's mental growth is not nurtured in this kind of environment. It is possible that these teenagers will not be able to respond appropriately to the various troubling situations that arise every day. They could be unable of handling challenges that arise in daily life.

Adolescents have a propensity to be easily angered and to get involved in harmful activities. They try to do things that are harmful for them in an effort to avoid disgrace or to gain prominence in the group. Adolescents who grow up in an emotionally and relationally unsatisfying family context are more likely to be easily angered and provoked. They act inappropriately because of the enormous emotional energy flowing through them. It might be quite difficult to hold back and keep quiet during adolescence.

Methodology

In this study, a systematic review of all the available literature was undertaken for the acquaintance of knowledge on the subject matter and to identify the parent-child relationship and emotional intelligence of adolescents. This paper draws an extensive literature review from 2010 to 2018. Secondary data were collected from articles, dissertations, thesis, and books.

Studies Conducted in India and Abroad on Parent-child Relationship and Emotional Intelligence of Adolescents

A literature review is a written summary of journal articles, books and other documents that describes the past and current state of information on the topic of research study. It helps the researcher to acquaint himself with current knowledge in the field or area in which he is going to conduct his research.

Melvina N. Amalui (2018) conducted research on "emotional intelligence as predictor of academic performance among secondary school students in Makurdi Metropolis of Benue State". The study came to the conclusion that there was a favourable association between emotional intelligence's components and secondary school students' academic achievement.

Hojjat (2017) investigated the impact of group training in emotional intelligence on anger in teenagers with drug-using fathers. Parents who abuse drugs often have children who struggle emotionally more. According to the study, teaching emotional intelligence skills can help teenagers whose father's abuse drugs control their anger.

Motamedi (2017) found that an emotional intelligence training programme could significantly raise emotional intelligence in adolescents with emotional and behavioural problems in single parent families. The study looked at the development of an emotional intelligence programme training and its effectiveness on emotional intelligence of adolescents with emotional and behavioural problems who live in single parent families.

Gomez-Baya et al. (2016) investigated the relationship between perceived emotional intelligence and depressive symptoms in adolescents following a one-year follow-up. The study's findings highlighted gender variations in depression symptoms and emotional intelligence, and they also suggested that after a year of follow-up, having more emotional intelligence is linked to fewer depressive symptoms. The rise in adolescent depressive symptoms highlights the need to develop programmes that prevent adolescent depression by encouraging the development of adaptive emotional skills.

Sharma (2014) research on adolescents resilience in connection to emotional intelligence, stress, parental attachment, and interpersonal reactivity, not all adolescents who experience traumatic events go on to have behavioural and mental health issues. In examining the significance of stress during adolescence, the study identified crucial elements in resilience, emotional intelligence, coping mechanisms, personality traits, and parental attachment that may aid in the smooth transition of teenagers into highly competent adults.

Arora and Kaur (2014) conducted research on adolescent's emotional stability in connection to parent-child relationships. The results of the study showed a positive and substantial association between the emotional stability of adolescents and the six aspects of parent-child relationships, including symbolic punishment, rejecting, object punishment, demanding, indifferent, and symbolic reward.

Shalini and Acharya (2013) in study of perceived parental parenting style on emotional intelligence of adolescents the results of study revealed that the father's authoritative and

authoritarian parenting style significantly correlated with emotional intelligence and fathers were perceived to be more authoritative towards girls than boys. Findings suggest the greater involvement of fathers and adopting an authoritative approach in bringing up emotionally intelligent adolescents.

Ruiz et al. (2013) examined the relational factors that are related to teenagers' usage of conflict resolution approaches by examining their attachment preferences and their parents' level of communication. A first observation is that adolescents generally tended to employ the three resolution strategies, they tended to feel more securely attached than insecurely attached, and they tended to communicate better with their mother than with their father. Additionally, when speaking and disputing with their mothers rather than their fathers, teens felt more under scrutiny and disagreements.

Keijsers&Poulin (2013) examined how parent-child communication evolved throughout the course of adolescence. According to the study, parental solicitation, teenage disclosure, and secrecy all declined in early adolescence, which led to a drop in parent-child contact. In middle adolescence, girls' communication with their parents became more frequent as evidenced by rising parental solicitation, rising adolescent disclosure, and falling teenage secrecy. Early in puberty, males' disclosure decreased, while solicitation and secrecy remained constant.

Salguero et al. (2012) examined adolescent assessments of their emotional intelligence as a predictor of their psychological adjustment. The study's findings indicated that perceived emotional intelligence is a reliable indicator of adolescent adjustment and may be a useful tool for early intervention.

Skaar& Williams (2012) looked at emotional intelligence as a predictor of teenage risk behaviour involvement and perception. The findings indicated that emotional intelligence is associated with some types of risky behaviour in younger teenagers, and that more advanced emotional intelligence skills may enable them to refrain from engaging in risky activity like drinking and driving. Among contrast, emotional intelligence among older teenagers is associated with risk perception rather than behaviour participation. Even though they view the action as having a higher risk value, older teenagers with high emotional intelligence may overcome social constraints.

Panwar (2012) study of the relationship between personality traits and academic achievement at the secondary level and evolving strategies for emotional management at different levels of emotional intelligence, students with high emotional intelligence perform better in this area than students with low emotional intelligence, and students with extroversion levels perform better than students with extroversion levels.

In his study of the interaction between families and secondary school students' emotional intelligence, *Bhatia (2012)* found that young people's emotional intelligence is highly influenced by their family relationships. An important link between emotional intelligence and parental approval was also found, according to the study.

Nastasa and Sala (2011) on adolescents' emotional intelligence and parenting practises, how parents communicate with their children has an impact on both how emotionally intelligent they

are as adults and how they interact with others. Teenagers' capacity to control their own emotions and impulses, to be more adaptable, and to communicate their feelings in an authoritative way is greatly influenced by the parenting style of the parents and the dynamics within the family.

Alegre (2011) investigated how parents raise their kids and their emotional intelligence. According to the study, parental responsiveness, emotion-related coaching, and positive demandingness are all associated to children's emotional intelligence being higher, while parental negative demandingness is related to children's emotional intelligence being lower. Parental attitudes and behaviours may influence children's emotional intelligence in the same or different ways as they influence other developmental outcomes.

Khajehpour (2011) investigated the connection between high school students' academic achievement, emotional intelligence, and parental participation. The findings showed a favourable and significant relationship between the participants' academic success, parental involvement, and emotional intelligence. This shows that parental participation and emotional intelligence may be predictive of high school adolescents' academic success.

Koneri (2010) found that high parental involvement has an impact on the emotional intelligence (EQ) components of interpersonal, stress management adaptability, general mood, positive impression, and total EQ of adolescents. Parental love is linked to the development of higher emotional intelligence, and parental care and support are both positively related to emotional intelligence.

A positive parent-child relationship has been linked to unexpected educational benefits, according to research by *Turley et al. (2010)*. While devoted parents may encourage in their kids two loyalties, namely to school and to family, the parent-child relationship and educational outcomes are not necessarily linked in a straightforward monotonous pattern. While students are still in elementary and secondary schools, these loyalties can coexist peacefully, but when they enter college, they may clash.

Conclusion

After reviewing past research on the parent-child relationship and emotional intelligence during the adolescent stage, it became clear that parental participation is crucial to children's adjustment and happiness. The research showed a general decline in parent-child communication during adolescence; nevertheless, a child's ability to communicate feelings aggressively is greatly influenced by the parenting style of their parents. The ability to control one's emotions is crucial to the effective development of adolescents into highly capable adults in the near future. The presence of depressive symptoms was shown to be reduced in children with a higher emotional quotient and higher in children with a lower emotional quotient.

It is emphasized how important emotional management is to a child's overall well-being. The research has shown that the child greatly depends on their parent's style of emotional expression for expressing their feelings, hence the importance of parent-child relationships during adolescence cannot be overlooked. It is clear from the data shown above, which were derived

from earlier studies that the investigator analysed, that both the parent-child relationship and emotional intelligence are very important and have a big impact on children's lives.

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